

A Study to Explore the Health Information System in Sri Lanka

Dilrukshi DARK¹, Ranga SDUM², Rajkumar

S³¹Senior Registrar, Medical Administration

²Senior Registrar, Medical Administration

³Post MD Fellow in Medical Administration, University of Oxford, United Kingdom

Abstract:

Health information systems (HIS) are important for planning policies, programmes and monitoring the impact of them. Finding data sources quickly for effective utilization of collected information are of vital importance in handling any HIS. With the starting of civil registration in 1868 Sri Lankan HIS has been developed and expanded covering many more important areas and had been utilized for health system improvement. Objective of this study was to explore the Sri Lankan HIS and identify the areas need to be improved as reliable information source. This qualitative study was done using a purposive sample of officials from Ministry of Health, Medical Statistics Unit and Registrar General Department as well as reviewing all the relevant accessible reliable literature. Sri Lankan health information system can be categorized in to two subsystems: population based and facility/Institutional based. Population-based HIS includes household surveys regularly conducted by the Department of Censuses and Statistics (DCS), and civil registration which is under Department of Registrar General (RGD). Facility-based HIS includes information from curative and preventive sector institutions such as clinical, health and management information systems. Findings revealed although the birth and death coverage are high, quality of cause of death information is still a major problem. Some non-functioning systems as scheduled, under reporting, duplication of data collection was identified as major issues. Many initiatives are suggested to improve the quality of cause of death information, including training regarding medical certification of cause of death based on ICD10 for the relevant officers and use of verbal autopsy procedure. Regulation of information surveillance from one focal point was recommended by the study to prevent duplication and resource wasting and optimal utilization of gathered data.

Key words; Health Information System, Data Management, Optimal Utilization

Introduction:

Health information is important in any country as it provides indicators to assess the health system. Health statistics developed based on those information systems are important for planning policies, programmes and monitoring the impact of them. Finding data sources for effective utilization of them are of vital importance in efficient and effective management of health system¹. Sri Lankan HIS has a long history, starting of civil registration in 1868 and population census in 1871. Up to now it has been developed and expanded covering many more important areas of health sector².

Sri Lankan health information system (HIS) can be categorized into two subsystems: population based and facility/Institutional based. Population-based HIS includes household surveys regularly conducted by the Department of Censuses and Statistics (DCS), and civil registration which is under Department of Registrar General (RGD). Facility-based HIS includes information from curative and preventive sector institutions such as clinical, health and management information systems³.

Objectives were to explore and study the evolution of HIS of Sri Lanka from its beginning to current situation and to identify areas need to be improved in HIS of Sri Lanka as more reliable source of information.

Methodology:

For this qualitative study Key informant interviews were done with relevant identified officials from health, RGD and medical statistic unit as a purposive sample. Literature reviewing was done through available relevant materials in the internet, newspapers, health manuals, books. Data collection was carried out during period of six months from 2018 January to 2018 June;

Results:

Mainly two types of HISs identified as population based and institutional based.

Population based HIS

Population-based HIS includes senses which are regularly conducted by the DCS and civil registration which is under RGD.

Census/ Surveys

Population and housing census: Sri Lanka has a long history of Census taking; started in 1871, 143 years ago. It was the first Population Census conducted among South Asian Countries. The census data reflects population distribution by Demographic characteristics with life expectancy, internal migration, functional difficulties, fertility etc.

(2). Demographic & Health Survey provides important information on Fertility, Family Planning, Maternal and Child Health, Nutrition and awareness of HIV/ AIDS(1)

Table 01. Census and Surveys related to health information which are conducted by National statistic department

	Census/ Survey	Started year	frequency	Latest year
1	Population and housing census	1871	10 years	2011/12
2	Demographic health survey	1987	6 years	2016
3	National Survey on Self- Reported Health in Sri Lanka- combined to annual National Labor Force Survey.	2014	One time	2014
4	Household Income and Expenditure Survey	1980/81	5 years	2016
5	Annual health Bulletin	1980	1 year	2018

In 2014, National Survey on Self- Reported Health in Sri Lanka provides information related to chronic illnesses, acute illness as well as some other health related issues useful to monitor policy impacts at household level⁴.

The household Income and Expenditure Survey gives information on health expenditure of the population and latest one was conducted in 2016 covering all 25 districts⁵.

Civil registration:

Sri Lanka has had a long history of civil registration covering the registration of births and deaths by Ordinance No.18 of 1867, which came into operation in June 1868, and became compulsory from 1897. The procedure laid down in this law continues with modifications

introduced from time to time. The current law came into operation in 1954⁶.

The father or mother of every child born alive is primarily responsible to give information to the Registrar of the division within 42 days for registration. It is the responsibility of the Officer-in-charge of a Government Hospital to give information in respect of all events occurring in his hospital. If the period of 42 days has lapsed, the birth can still be registered within three months from the date of occurrence.

Information of death should be given to the Registrar of the division within 05 days of its occurrence. According to the law, the obligation for giving information rests on the nearest relative present at death, however, a

death can still be registered free of charge within three months of its occurrence.

The Superintendent of the estate is bounded by the law to reports of births & deaths to the appropriate District Registrar (Divisional Secretary) through the Estate Medical Officer. All births & deaths occurring in private hospitals, non-Government Institutions, Nursing Homes, Private Houses, should be registered upon information given by qualified informants. It is the duty of every Grama Niladhari to inform himself of all births & deaths occurring in his division and to furnish a report in the prescribed form direct to the appropriate registrars².

Facility/ Institution-based HIS

Facility based HIS includes information from curative and preventive sector institutions such as clinical, health and management information systems. Facility based HIS system gain information mainly from Hospital information system/ Curative sector, Public HIS/ preventive sector and Surveys which are conducted by health ministry- routinely and intermittently for special purposes.

Hospital information systems

Mainly seven types of information are gathered by Medical Statistics Unit from the curative sector.

Table 2: Health information gathered by Medical Statistic Unit

Type of Information	Frequency of collection
1. Maternal Statistics Return (H 830)	Monthly
2. Monthly Dental Return (H 1201)	Monthly
3. Indoor Morbidity and Mortality Return	Quarterly
4. Outdoor Patient Return	Quarterly
5. Clinic Return	Quarterly
6. Number of specialists and other Hospital Staff return (SSR 400)	Annually
7. Number of Beds by Wards (BSR 300)	Annually

(Source- medical statistic unit, MoH)

Curative sector information is mainly obtained through Indoor morbidity and mortality returns (IMMR), e-IMMR is implementing in 80% of curative care institutions throughout the country. In outdoor patient return provide information about number of patients with the relevant visit. There are only limited numbers of diseases in clinic return list, though there are many more new diseases.

Other institutional HIS

In Sri Lanka, there is well established information system extending from the grass root level to the central level for MCH activities. This Reproductive Health Management Information System (RHMIS) was initiated in 1986 by Family Health Bureau (FHB), and currently developing a web-based e-RHIMS to replace the existing paper based system⁷.

Table 3: Other information collecting systems within the Health Ministry

Information system	Type of information	Responsible Unit
1. Reproductive Health Management System (RHMIS) e-RHMIS	Health Surveillance of Maternal and Newborn care Information	FHB
2. Family planning quarterly return	Data on Family planning methods	FHB
3. Quarterly school health return	Data on school health programme	FHB
4. Maternal death surveillance and response system	Maternal death investigation data	FHB
5. National fetio-infant mortality surveillance system	fetio-infant mortality data	FHB
6. Annual data sheet of MOHs	MOH coverage/performance	FHB
7. annual Nutrition month report	Mal nutrition and Obesity of target groups	FHB
8. Monthly return from Therapist	Dental Therapist coverage/performance	FHB
9. Quarterly EPI returns	WEBIIS Surveillance of EPI programme	Epidemiology Unit
10. DenSys (Web-based)	Surveillance of Dengue patients	Epidemiology Unit

11. FluSys (Web-based)	Surveillance of Influenza patients	Epidemiology unit
12. National communicable disease surveillance system. (Web-based NCDSS)	Prevalence of common NCDs	Epidemiology Unit
13. Oral Health Survey	Prevalence of Oral diseases, And Oral health Staff	DDG- Dental Services Unit
14. Injury Surveillance	Surveillance of different type of Injury patients	DDG- NCD Unit
15. Cancer Surveillance	Surveillance of different Cancer Patients	National Cancer Control programme
16. MS-MIS (Web-based)	Connect MSD with RMSD and Line ministry institutions	MSD

(Table 3(cont.): Other information collecting systems within the Health Ministry)

Expanded Programme of Immunization (EPI) of Sri Lanka is one of the best performing public health programme since 1978 in the region and as well as in the world. There is web-based system to collect quarterly EPI return called WEBIIS in Sri Lanka⁸.

Information on other public health concern diseases such as Dengue, Leprosy, Tuberculosis etc. are sent to the relevant specialized unit or campaign.

Epidemiology Unit of MoH responsible for prevention and control of communicable diseases. The Unit handles this task through a well-established and widely accepted

disease surveillance system with a sound legal basis. There are 27 communicable diseases which are mandatory to notify to the Epidemiological unit⁹. Optionally there is a “web based national communicable disease surveillance system.” Epidemiology unit publish weekly, quarterly and annual epidemiological report of communicable diseases.

Annual Health Bulletin is the official publication of the MoH since 1980 by the medical statistics unit. It is the only comprehensive report which gives the overall information on health sector in Sri Lanka, covering four major areas, Morbidity,

Mortality, Resource availability and Provision of services¹⁰.

There are specialized surveys like Oral health survey which was started in 1983/84 (11) are conducted by different units of the health ministry., Facility Survey and Human Resource Management Information System (HRHIMS) are conducted by the management development and planning unit for the administrative and planning purposes. National health account report also published intermittently by MoH.

Issues relate to HIS

Majority of participants identified following as main issues need to be addressed during KII. They were mentioned top to bottom as identified priority order.

- Delaying of data receiving from relevant institutions.
- Incompleteness and low quality of some data
- Inability of using some information systems as reliable source not updating them as scheduled.
- Duplication of data collection
- HR and infrastructure issues relate to information system maintaining.
- Lack of supervision and commitment from higher authorities.

- Data generating level officials not having initial awareness regarding importance of sending data.
- Information collecting forms are not user friendly.

Discussion:

This study was intended to explore the HIS from its beginning and identify the areas need to be improved to function as reliable information source. This was a qualitative study done through key informant interviews using purposive sample of health officials, officer from RGD and medical statistic unit as well as referring all reliable available data sources on HIS.

Mainly two types of HISs identified as population based and Institutional based. Population based system was further divided in to two as household surveys and civil registration system. This is similar to the Thailand HIS¹² may be due to influence of early British colonization. IMMR, EPI surveillance, Maternal and newborn care surveillance and notifiable disease surveillance can be mentioned as main institutional based systems. Population based system is driven by DCS (Census) and RGD (Civil Registration). When comparing Japan HIS, this above information is collected by the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communication, most of other health information are collect, compile and analyze

by the MoH similar to the Sri Lankan system¹⁴.

The study revealed that although the birth and death coverage is high, quality of cause of death information is still a major problem. Many initiatives are suggested to improve the quality of cause of death information, including training regarding medical certification of cause of death based on ICD10 for the relevant officers, the use of verbal autopsy to verify cause of death. It was revealed there was a information delay in civil registration system, to overcome that mutually sharing birth related information between WEBIIS and e-population project of the RGD was tried¹³.

During the study it was revealed even though web based electronic system is available still there are issues regarding quality of the diagnosis of IMMR and delaying of data provision. Lack of infrastructure facilities, shortage of trained MROs, BHTs not receiving timely to the record rooms, incorrect diagnosis due to lack of awareness of ICD classification and missing BHTs are identified as root causes.

There was no mechanism to collect information on diagnosis regarding patient treated by OPD and clinic return need to be updated to match the current trends.

The study identified that information on private sector including hospital belongs to forces; police hospital and indigenous treatment centers were not included to get comprehensive picture on disease burden of the country. As an initial step to overcome this problem, e-IMMR system had been introduced to some leading private hospitals with the hope of expanding to other institutions.

Furthermore, the study revealed some nonfunctioning information systems such as facility surveys and HRMIS surveillance and under reporting of some new information collecting systems such as injury surveillance system. It also revealed duplication of information collections. Therefore, it will be more beneficial all the information in one common system which can be used by all the units of the ministry.

Conclusion:

Sri Lankan HIS has been developed and expanded to cover many different areas of health system assessing level of service provision and population health. However, there are some areas to be improved to optimize the coverage, reliability and quality of data.

References

1. Department of census and statistics -Sri Lanka(online), Available at; <http://www.statistics.gov.lk/page.asp?page=Health>
2. P. G. Swarna Neunbella, L. Padmini de Silva, T. H. J. Fernando “Sri Lanka: current status of vital statistics and civil registration system” DCS, Ministry of Plan Implementation and Department of Registrar General November, 1993.
3. Health in Transition, country report Sri Lanka. 2nd chapter, (unpublished)
4. National Survey on Self- Reported Health in Sri Lanka-labour force survey 2014
5. Households Income and Expenditure Survey, Sri Lanka, 2016; Census and Statistic Department, Sri Lanka.
6. Registrar Generals department; Sri Lanka (online); Available at; <http://www.rgd.gov.lk/web/index.php/en/component/content/article/8-about-us/6-overview.html>
7. Annual report of Family Health Bureau- 2017, Family Health Bureau, MoH, Sri Lanka.
8. Director General of Health Services, Implementation of submission of web-based EPI quarterly return, circular No: EPID/417/2011/MH, Ministry of Health Sri Lanka; 17/11/2014.
9. Epidemiology Unit, MoH Sri Lanka (online), Available at; www.epid.gov.lk
10. Annual health bulletin 2015, MoH, Sri Lanka.
11. Oral Health Survey report, MoH, Sri Lanka, 2016
12. Health System review, The Kingdom of Thailand of, Health in transition; Vol. 5; No 52015; page 30-35.
13. Director General of Health, Implementation of Birth Registration Module of the WEBIIS;, circular No; EPID/417/2011/MH: dated 25/11/2014
14. Japan Health System Review, Health System in Transition: Vol 8: No. 12018: page 34